

OXYMORON: EXPRESSING IDEAS THROUGH CONTRADICTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13954524>

ANNOTATION

This article focuses on the study of the phenomenon of oxymoron and examines its place in language and literature, theoretical foundations and forms of application. Oxymoron is a stylistic device created by the use of words with contradictory or opposite meanings in one place. It is used not only in literature, but also in advertising and everyday communication. The article provides various examples of oxymoron and discusses their importance in expressing feelings, thoughts and events. Oxymorons evokes strong emotions in literature and help to increase the complexity of the text.

Key words: oxymoron, contradiction, theoretical foundations, literature, philosophy, cognitive semantics, postmodernism, emotion, complexity, linguistics

INTRODUCTION: Oxymoron is a stylistic device widely used in language and literature, which is formed by the use of words that contradict each other or have opposite meanings. This methodological tool helps to express the idea in a deeper and more complex way. Oxymoron arouses interest and wonder among readers and listeners, so they are widely used in literature, art, and ordinary speech.

METHOD: This article examines the oxymoron phenomenon from its theoretical foundations to its place and various uses in literature and discourse. Oxymorons are divided into two main types:

Simple oxymorons: Phrases based on simple contrasts. For example: "yengil og'irlik", "qorong'u yorug'lik", "mo"jiza qiyin".

Literary oxymorons: In literature, it is used to reflect complex emotions and the development of characters. Examples: "hayotning o'limi" (O. Xayyam), "tiqilinchda sokinlik" (F. Dostoevskiy).

RESULTS: Oxymoron is used in literature to evoke strong emotions, to make the content of texts interesting and complex. They draw the attention of the reader by increasing the contradictions between events and characters. For example, the expression "happiest girl" represents the contradiction between greed and happiness.

Oxymoron is also widely used in advertising and everyday communication. For example, "abadiy vaqt" yoki "keng tor" kabi iboralar ziddiyat orqali mahsulotni taqdim etadi.

Now we will analyze oxymoron in English with examples:

For example, the phrase *deafening silence* in English is an example of an oxymoron, because the words "*deafening*" and "*silence*" are combined in this phrase. The lexeme of *sukut*\silence in this phrase is expressed very strongly in the sense of waiting for something in silence, which in itself implies a strong emotional state. This phrase is mostly used when one is feeling a state of being, for example, waiting for some change or event.

Another bitter-sweet expression is the words *bitter* in the sense of *achchiq* and *sweet*\shirin in the opposite way, and this expression can reflect, for example, good and bad memories together. At the same time, emotions are opposite, but they complement each other.

If we cite examples of oxymoron in Uzbek, for example, let's analyze the phrase *Sukunat shovqini*.

Analysis: The words *sukunat* (*sukut*)\silence and *shovqin*\noise are contradictory. This phrase is used to describe internal or external noise, movement and emotions, for example, although there should be peace in a place. It is usually used when there are strong emotions or problems.

Let's analyze the Uzbek phrase *chiroyli*\beautiful *xafa*\sad:

Analysis: the words *Chiroyli* (*go'zal*) and *xafa* (*xafa*) complete each other. This expression means that a person may be beautiful on the outside, but on the inside may be bad or sad. This oxymoron is often used to express self-awareness and emotional state.

So, oxymoron, in general, combine two different feelings or concepts in a sentence or phrase to create a strong figurative meaning. This stylistic device helps readers or listeners gain a deeper understanding of an action or emotion. The juxtaposition of two opposing concepts is a powerful tool for refreshing thoughts and expressing complex feelings about any event or situation.

ARGUMENT. Oxymoron can also be studied within theories such as cognitive semantics and postmodernism. They provide an opportunity to express feelings and thoughts in a complex situation. Oxymoron plays an important role not only in literature, but also in the fields of psychology, politics, and aesthetics. For example, the phrase "urush tinchlikdir\war is peace" reflects political contradiction and the complexity of reality.

References:

1. J. D. Salinger - "The Catcher in the Rye": "Deafening silence" (quloqni yutadigan sukut)
2. William Shakespeare - "Romeo and Juliet": "Bitter sweet" (achchiq-shirin)
3. T. S. Eliot - "The Love Song of J. Alfred Prufrock": "In the room the women come and go talking of Michelangelo"
4. George Orwell - "1984": "War is peace" (urush tinchlikdir)
5. Emily Dickinson - "Hope is the thing with feathers": "Hope is a thing with feathers" (umid - parvona)